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THE INFLUENCE OF EXTRAGENITAL PATHOLOGY OF THE MOTHER ON THE PROCESSES OF FERTILITY AND THE FORMATION OF THE IMMUNE SYSTEM OF THE OFFSPRING

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Abstract

The influence of extra genital pathology on the reproductive function of female rats and the structural and functional development of the immune system of the offspring was researched. More pronounced violations of reproductive function were found in females with chronic toxic hepatitis (CTH) than in autoimmune enterocolitis (AIE). The appearance of prenatal mortality in females, an increase in mortality of rat pups on days 1-3 after birth, a lag in the development of offspring, in the form of a decrease in growth and weight indicators, the mass of internal organs of rat pups, were also more pronounced in the group with CTG. Deeper structural and functional changes in early postnatal ontogenesis associated with a lag in the development of the thymus, spleen, mesenteric lymph nodes and Peyer's patches before the transition of rat pups to mixed and definitive nutrition is also characteristic of the offspring of CTG females.

Keywords: hepatitis, enterocolitis, mother, offspring, early postnatal ontogenesis, development, thymus, spleen, mesenteric lymph nodes, Peyer's patches.

It is known that the full development of a newborn directly depends on the state of health of the mother and father during the period of conception, and then completely on the state of the mother during pregnancy and postpartum lactation [13, 14, 25, 27]. However, in recent years, the frequency of various extra genital diseases in women of childbearing age tends to increase. First, this applies to diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, in particular, to lesions of the hepatobiliary system due to viral hepatitis and chronic enterocolitis [1, 3, 8, 19]. It has been established that chronic lesions of the mother's liver cause various changes in hematological parameters, cellular and humoral immunity in the offspring [22]. The consequences of chronic enterocolitis are anemia, hypovitaminosis among women of childbearing age, which naturally have a negative impact on the development of offspring. At the same time, in the literature available to us, information regarding the influence of chronic liver damage and chronic enterocolitis of the mother on the structural foundations of the formation of the organs of immunogens of the offspring could not be found. Meanwhile, the solution of this problem would make it possible to understand the mechanisms of immunodeficiency in children born to mothers with liver damage and chronic enterocolitis and to substantiate the preventive correction and prevention of possible diseases in children.

The purpose of the research was to study the effect of chronic heliothral hepatitis and chronic autoimmune enterocolitis on the reproductive function of female rats and the structural state of the organs of the immune system of their offspring during early postnatal ontogenesis.

Materials and methods

The experiments were carried out on 120 mature female white outbred rats weighing 170-190 g. The animals were divided into 3 groups (40 rats in each): the control group (K), the first experimental group with chronic toxic hepatitis (CTH) and the second experimental group with autoimmune enterocolitis (AIE). The study followed the "Principles for the Care of Laboratory Animals" (NIH Publication No. 85-23, revised 1985). The CTG model was obtained according to the generally accepted method [1], by weekly administration of 0.05 mg of heliothrin per 1 g of animal body weight for 6 weeks. The control group received sterile saline instead of heliothrin.

The tissue antigen for reproducing experimental auto allergic or autoimmune enterocolitis, that is, for the second experimental group, was a homologous, homogenized suspension of the mucous membrane of the large and small intestines on complete Freund's adjuvant. For immunization, 0.5 ml of this antigen was thoroughly mixed with 0.5 ml of warmed complete adjuvant and injected subcutaneously weekly for 6 weeks.

The control group received sterile saline instead of heliothrin [3]. Ten days after the last injection, males were added to the females of all three groups. Subsequently, the course of pregnancy was monitored. For the research, only 180 cubs from females of the control and experimental groups were used (60 from each group).

The rat pups were decapitated under light ether anesthesia on days 1, 3, 7, 15, 21, and 30 after birth. To study the mass of animals and internal organs, electronic scales with a resolution of up to 0.0001 grams were used. To conduct morphological researches, pieces of the thymus, mesenteric lymph nodes, spleen and Peyer's patches were fixed in 12% neutral formalin or Bouin's liquid, which, after appropriate wiring, were embedded in paraffin. For morphological and morphometric studies, sections 5-7 μm thick were used stained with hematoxylin and eosin.

Results

The results of our research showed that chronic toxic hepatitis and autoimmune enterocolitis, caused in female rats before pregnancy, leads to some disturbances in the processes of fertilization and development of offspring. First, it should be noted that CTG and AIE have a significant negative effect on the mother's body, in particular, on the fertility and course of pregnancy in female rats. In the control group, all animals (100%) became pregnant, which successfully ended in childbirth. However, in 84% of rats with CTH, pregnancy ended in childbirth in 64%, miscarriages - in 8%. The rest died during pregnancy. The average number of pups from one mother in the control group was 9.7 ± 0.5 , while in the group from CTG females it was 6.3 ± 0.6 . In females with CTG, the postnatal mortality of the offspring increased to 39.6% (against the control of 6.2%). Moreover, the highest mortality (28.7%) was observed on the 1-7th day after birth (5.4% in the control).

In the research of the reproductive function of females with AIE, a 10% afertility was found. In the rest of the females, 87.7% of the pregnancies ended successfully in childbirth, and in 2.3% of cases, there were miscarriages. The average number of pups in the litter from females with chronic enterocolitis was 7.76 ± 0.52 , which is 1.2 times lower than in control animals. Along with this, it should also be noted that the increase in postnatal mortality of rat pups to 9.5% (6.2% control), of which 5.6% on days 1-3 and 1.9% on days 3-7 after birth (with control 4.9% and 0.70% respectively).

The research of the anthropometric parameters of the studied groups of animals showed (see Table) that in rat pups born from CTG females there is a decrease in weight relative to the control group up to 7 days of development (an average of 9% relative to the control data), while when measuring body length, a lag was found in growth on the first day after birth on the 15th day of development (by 12% and up to 20%, respectively). The research of the mass of internal organs showed a decrease in the mass of the thymus only in newborn rat pups (by 22%), while the mass of the spleen decreased in newborns (by 24%) and on the 15th day after birth (up to 22%) and the liver in newborns and 3 day old rat pups (by 22% relative to the control group of animals). A relatively less pronounced lag in anthropometric data was noted in AIE females. Thus, a decrease in body weight was noted from birth and only up to 3 days of development (on average by 5%), body length was noted only starting from 7 days (by 2%), on the 15th day after birth (up to 7%). In the offspring born from enterocolitis females, when examining the mass of internal organs, a decrease in only the mass of the spleen in newborns (from 22%) and only up to 7 days of development (by 21%), and the liver to 9% at birth (from 2%) and up to 3 days of development (up to 9%).

Table

Increase in body weight and some internal organs of rat pups of the control and experimental groups in the dynamics of early postnatal ontogenesis ($X \pm x_m$)

Indicator	Group of animals	Timing of postnatal development					
		1 day	3 days	7 days	15 days	21 days	30 days
Body mass (gram)	C	5,6 $\pm$ 0,06	6,0 $\pm$ 0,09	8,9 $\pm$ 0,11	18,6 $\pm$ 0,43	29,1 $\pm$ 0,82	45,33 $\pm$ 1,51
	CTG	5,1$\pm$0,12	5,3$\pm$0,11	8,1$\pm$0,12	16,9 $\pm$ 0,42	26,8 $\pm$ 0,55	41,7 $\pm$ 1,53
	CAE	5,3$\pm$0,04	5,6$\pm$0,08	8,5 $\pm$ 0,14	17,6 $\pm$ 0,41	27,7 $\pm$ 0,76	45,2 $\pm$ 1,61
Body length (mm)	C	27,1 $\pm$ 0,47	33,0 $\pm$ 0,58	44,2 $\pm$ 0,53	51,6 $\pm$ 0,52	55,2 $\pm$ 0,97	57,6 $\pm$ 1,66
	CTG	23,9$\pm$0,43	27,1$\pm$0,52	36,4$\pm$0,51	41,5$\pm$0,61	47,6 $\pm$ 1,12	51,6 $\pm$ 1,23
	CAE	25,4 $\pm$ 0,52	30,3 $\pm$ 0,60	40,5$\pm$0,58	47,8$\pm$0,46	49,4 $\pm$ 1,00	54,3 $\pm$ 1,48
Thymus (mg)	C	10,1 $\pm$ 0,33	18,1 $\pm$ 0,59	26,4 $\pm$ 0,75	78,5 $\pm$ 1,42	133,0 $\pm$ 4,62	221,0 $\pm$ 5,94
	CTG	7,9$\pm$0,07	15,8 $\pm$ 0,46	22,9 $\pm$ 0,69	68,9 $\pm$ 1,12	104,6 $\pm$ 4,13	181,6 $\pm$ 3,54
	CAE	8,4 $\pm$ 0,28	17,5 $\pm$ 0,85	24,4 $\pm$ 1,13	76,3 $\pm$ 3,6	119,6 $\pm$ 3,67	199,9 $\pm$ 20,23
Spleen (mg)	C	7,4 $\pm$ 0,32	20,9 $\pm$ 0,79	31,6 $\pm$ 1,00	67,7 $\pm$ 2,92	78,6 $\pm$ 3,58	138,1 $\pm$ 4,84
	CTG	5,6$\pm$0,23	16,2$\pm$0,32	23,4$\pm$0,96	52,5$\pm$2,15	69,2 $\pm$ 4,34	125,6 $\pm$ 5,13
	CAE	6,2$\pm$0,22	18,5$\pm$0,37	28,0$\pm$0,76	60,0 $\pm$ 2,43	71,9 $\pm$ 5,94	126,8 $\pm$ 6,3
Liver (mg)	C	150,6 $\pm$ 5,33	228,3 $\pm$ 5,52	234,1 $\pm$ 10,49	468,0 $\pm$ 18,96	1062,8 $\pm$ 40,64	1725,5 $\pm$ 173,77
	CTG	117,9$\pm$5,12	199,8$\pm$5,32	206,6 $\pm$ 7,14	405,9 $\pm$ 14,53	986,4 $\pm$ 43,44	1512,6 $\pm$ 136,65
	CAE	131,5$\pm$3,11	210,0$\pm$3,81	220,3 $\pm$ 7,94	427,9 $\pm$ 15,23	1003,8 $\pm$ 63,56	1557,3 $\pm$ 209,69

Note: 1. Conventional abbreviations: Gr. well. - a group of animals; Counter - offspring from the control group of females; CAE - offspring from females with autoimmune enterocolitis; CTG - offspring from females with chronic heliothrine hepatitis. 2. Indicators where the differences are significant relative to the control at $P < 0.05$ are in bold.

The conducted morphological researches made it possible to establish that the thymus is sufficiently formed in newborn rat pups of the control group. The cortical and medulla are clearly differentiated. The distribution density of cells in the cortex is greater than in the medulla. Thymocytes, macrophages, and reticuloepitheliocytes differentiate among the cells. In the medulla, reticuloepitheliocytes predominate, while thymocytes are much less. Hassall's corpuscles are very rare. (See Fig. 1).

Mesenteric lymph nodes are represented by diffuse accumulations of lymphocytes and other mononuclear cells in the reticular stroma. Lymphoid follicles are not yet formed. The absence of formed structural and functional zones is also characteristic of other peripheral organs of the immune system. The spleen during this period is mainly the organ of erythro- and thrombopoiesis. The parenchyma of the organ mainly

consists of a red pulp, in which numerous erythroblastic islands are located. There is no formed white pulp (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3). In Peyer's patches, there is also a diffuse distribution of mononuclear cells throughout the stroma in the absence of clear boundaries of lymphoid follicles. On the 7-15th day of the postnatal period, differentiation of the cortical and medulla is noted in the mesenteric lymph nodes. Simultaneously, the formation of lymphoid follicles. In the spleen, also during this period, the formation of lymphatic nodules and differentiation in them of the marginal and periarterial zones are observed. The formation of lymphoid follicles also occurs in Peyer's patches. On the 21-30th day of postnatal ontogenesis, the formation of structural and functional zones of peripheral organs of immunogenesis is completed, where the processes of lymphocyto-, plasmacytopoiesis and antibody formation are already taking place in full.

Figure 1. 15 day old rat pups from control group females. Cross section of thymus lobules. Formed thymus lobules are visible, clearly limited by connective tissue trabeculae. In the lobules, the cortical and cerebral zones are determined. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 100.

Figure 2. 7-day-old rat pups from females of the control group. Cross section of the spleen. A red pulp, with trabeculae and reticuloepitheliocytes located in it, which form the basis of the organ, mainly represents the spleen. Among which are cells at various stages of hemocytopoiesis. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 100.

Figure 3. 7-day-old rat pups from females of the control group. Cross section of the spleen. The section shows that the spleen of a rat is represented mainly by red pulp. Foci of hematopoiesis are visible, many cells at various stages of hemocytopoiesis. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 200.

In the first experimental group, CTG leads to pronounced structural disturbances in the processes of postnatal formation of the organs of the immune system in offspring. In particular, it was found that the thymus of newborn rat pups of this group is characterized by an indistinct lobular structure, a decrease in the cortical zone due to an increase in the proportion of the brain. In subsequent periods, some development of the thymus structures does not compensate for the slowdown in the postnatal formation of the organ. Compared with the control group, the number of lymphoblasts decreased by 15%, small lymphocytes - by 20%. This

trend persisted in subsequent terms of postnatal development of the thymus. Attention is drawn to the increase in the number of destructive thymocytes, which at various times after birth were 2-3 times higher than the indicators of the control group. Along with this, on sections of the thymus of the experimental group, much more often than in the control, there were large macrophages with dense inclusions in the cytoplasm, apparently also a sign of enhanced thymocytolysis (see Fig. 4 and Fig. 5). The severity of the described changes decreased only by the 30th day of postnatal ontogenesis. In the peripheral organs of the immune system of rat pups from females with CTH, there was a significant

delay in the postnatal formation of structural and functional zones. On the 7-15th day of the experiments, the parenchyma of the lymph node consisted mainly of diffuse lymphoid tissue without clear boundaries of the cortex and medulla. The subcapsular sinuses were significantly dilated. The absence of formed lymphatic follicles during this period is also characteristic of the spleen and Peyer's patches. On the 15th day, only the formation of small lymphoid follicles in the peripheral organs was noted in the rat pups of the experimental group. Sufficiently formed lymphatic follicles were detected in the control group during this period. By the 21st day of the postnatal period, in rat pups of the experimental group, the lymphoid tissue of the lymph

nodes, spleen, Peyer's patches remained hypoplastic, without clear boundaries of the various structural zones of the lymph follicles. Even by the 30th day of postnatal ontogenesis, the structural and functional development of Peyer's plaques remained from those of rat pups born from females of the control group (see Fig. 6).

A somewhat different picture is observed when studying the morphological formation of the above organs of offspring born from females with AIE. In newborn rat pups, the differentiation of the thymus into the cortical and medulla is quite clearly expressed. However, the distribution density of cells in the cortex is markedly reduced.

Figure 4. 15 day old rat pups from females of the CTG group. Cross section of thymus lobules. Formed thymus lobules are visible, with thinned connective tissue septa. In the lobules, the prevalence of the cortical zone over the brain zone is determined. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 100.

Figure 5. 15-day-old rat pups from females of the CTG group. Cross section of a thymus lobule. The brain area of the thymus lobules, all types of lymphocytes and reticuloepithelial cells, as well as Hassall's bodies formed by an accumulation of epithelial cells, are determined. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 200.

Figure 6. 30-day-old rat pups from females of the CTG group. Cross section of the ileum of the small intestine with Peyer's patch. The section shows the formed Peyer's plaque with clearly differentiated zones, which is characterized by the absence of villi in the dome-shaped zone, the lymphoid follicle, the parafollicular zone, however, it should be noted that the reactive center of the follicle is not yet very developed. Paraffin cut. Magnification x 100.

Mesenteric lymph nodes were represented by diffuse lymphoid tissue, without signs of differentiation into the cortical and cerebral zones, only on the 14-21st day of development processes of differentiation of structural formations of the cortical and cerebral zones

were noted. The spleen is characterized by underdevelopment of the white pulp, expressed in a relative decrease in the number and size of lymphoid follicles, and a slight increase in the functional activity of the red pulp. In the further dynamics of postnatal ontogenesis,

starting from the 21st day of development, some activation of the white pulp of the spleen is noted, in particular, a relative increase in the number of lymphoid follicles, an increase in their size, an increase in mitotic figures in T- and B-dependent zones. However, even in 30-day-old rat pups, the number of white pulp follicles and their size reach only the lower limit of the data obtained from control animals. We also found that in the experimental group of newborn rats, the rate of formation of the structural and functional zones of Peyer's patches is also significantly slowed down compared to the control group. Thus, the number of Peyer's patches in rats of the control group on the 14th day reached an average of 11.2 per length of the small intestine, while in the experimental group this figure was only 6.2. In the control group of rats, already on the 7th day in Peyer's patches, the presence of formed lymphatic follicles, the dome zone and parafollicular zones was noted, however, at the same time, in experimental rat pups in Peyer's patches, the presence of only diffuse lymphoid tissue was noted, without a clear division into structural and functional zones. Also, on the 7th day after birth, in the Peyer's patches of the control group of animals, T- and B-dependent zones were clearly distinguished, while in the plaques of rat pups from females with AIE, the differentiation of these zones ended only on days 21-30 after birth.

Discussion of the obtained data

Analyzing the obtained results, it should be noted that during pregnancy, normal growth and development of the fetus occurs due to complex, genetically determined immunological mechanisms for ensuring reproduction and reliability of the mother-placenta-fetus functional system [5, 7, 21 and 25]. After childbirth, the functional system mother-mammary gland-newborn is switched on, that is, the only organ that connects the body of the mother and the newborn and provides it not only with nutrients and biologically active substances, but also involved in the transfer of adaptive immunity to the infant is the mammary glands [2, 8, 13 and 27]. Nevertheless, this completely harmonious system of immunological relationships between mother and fetus, as well as between mother and newborn, is disrupted by maternal pathology during pregnancy and breastfeeding, which largely determine the course of the perinatal period of a child's development and, possibly, his entire life [9, 17].

With CTG, profound changes in metabolic processes occur in the body of a female, including a violation of protein metabolism, which naturally affects the hormonal balance, and, consequently, the development of the placenta and mammary gland, as well as developing offspring. If we also take into account the immunodeficient state of the mother in hepatitis, the violation of the detoxification function of the liver becomes clear, what is the reason for the lag in the digestive and immune systems of the offspring, established by many researchers [1, 7, and 17]. It has also been established that experimental chronic heliotrine hepatitis is an aggressive hepatitis, in which, in the process of chronization of the process, after the inclusion of autoimmune processes, there is an aggravation of the inflammatory process in the liver up to the transition of hepatitis to cirrhosis [4]. In addition, it has also been shown that in toxic heliotrine hepatitis there is a violation of the T-

system of immunity, which in turn contributes to auto-immunization of the body against antigens of its own liver. If we also take into account the pregnancy of the female, which is an additional burden on the body, and therefore on the liver, this further aggravates the situation. Summarizing all the above causal relationships, we can assume that they could contribute to the negative impact on both the mother's body and the developing offspring, discovered because of our study.

It has been established that during AIE in female rats it contributes to disruption of the processes of hydrolysis and absorption in the intestine, which in turn affects metabolic processes and leads to protein-vitamin and microelement deficiencies and anemia [6, 10, 19] in the mother's body. In addition, it should be noted that the intestine is involved in a wide range of processes that determine the adaptation of the body to external environmental factors. The main role in these processes belongs to the intestinal ecosystem, which consists of three components: host cells, nutrients and intestinal microflora. Newborns do not have full immunocompetence, since the synthesis of immunoglobulins does not begin until six months of age. In addition to maternal antibodies present in the blood of a newborn, breast milk is a good source of antibodies in the first months of life [21, 24]. In our case, in chronic autoimmune enterocolitis, inflammatory processes occurring in the intestine contribute to changes in the intestinal microbiota, which also lead to disruption of both the processes of assimilation of food in the mother's body and the supply of adequate nutrition through milk to the newborn. The immunodeficient situation in the mother's body has an immunosuppressive effect on the formation of the immune organs of rat pups [15, 16, 26]. Most likely, the consequence of the above processes, and established by us and shown in our previous works, are negative changes in the childbearing function of the mother and the lag in the development of the body and organs, including the immune system of the offspring in the period of early postnatal development. Consequently, the immune organs of rat pups begin to form intensively only after the transition of animals to mixed feeding and reach the lower limits of the morphometric parameters of control animals only by 30 days after birth.

Conclusions

1. Extra genital pathology of female rats has a negative effect on the reproductive function, where in chronic heliotrine hepatitis in females there is up to 16% affertility and an increase in postnatal mortality of the offspring by more than 5 times, with the highest mortality observed on the 1-3rd day after birth, while cases of affertility among females with autoimmune enterocolitis were only 10%, and on the 1st-3rd day of postnatal development, a 1.5-fold increase in mortality of rat pups was noted compared with the litter of females of the control group.

2. Chronic toxic hepatitis in female rats led to more pronounced disorders in the development of rat pups, compared to females with autoimmune chronic enterocolitis. This was expressed in the lagging of the growth and weight parameters of the rat pups themselves, as well as the mass of internal organs: thymus, spleen and liver relative to the rat pups from the females of the control group.

3. In offspring from females with extra genital pathology, there is a lag in the formation and development

of the thymus, mesenteric lymph nodes, spleen and Peyer's plaques, which are characterized by hypoplasia, a lag in the timing of the formation of structural and functional zones and formations on which the immune reactivity of the body depends in the dynamics of early postnatal ontogenesis, the most pronounced in the group of animals with CTG.

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